

LATITUDINAL SPECIES RICHNESS TIES IN WITH LONGITUDINAL SPECIES RICHNESS IN FOREST RED MILLIPEDES (DIPLOPODA: PACHYBOLIDAE)

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Article History

Received: 22.08.2024

Accepted: 17.09.2024

Published: 07.10.2024

Abstract: Latitude was tested for correlation with longitude in red millipedes *Centrobolus*. Latitude correlated with longitude in *Centrobolus* ($r=0.73$, Z score=5.68, $n=40$, $p=0.00000001$). Latitude correlated with species richness ($r=-0.97$, Z score=-12.54, $n=40$, $p=0$). Longitude correlated with species richness ($r=0.49$, Z score=3.27, $n=40$, $p=0.00054590$). Latitudinal species richness correlated with longitudinal species richness in *Centrobolus* ($r=0.3794$, $r^2=0.1439$, $n=40$, $p=0.01576$).

Keywords: *Centrobolus*, latitude, longitude, Red Millipedes, species.

Cite this article:

Cooper, M. I., (2024). LATITUDINAL SPECIES RICHNESS TIES IN WITH LONGITUDINAL SPECIES RICHNESS IN FOREST RED MILLIPEDES (DIPLOPODA: PACHYBOLIDAE). *ISAR Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 2(10), 15-40.

Introduction

Red millipedes are distributed in the southern African subregion from 17° latitude S and -35° latitude S. They have been well studied recently [1-440] with taxonomically important species comprising 12 species threatened, nine vulnerable, and three endangered [440]. They can be found in all the forests of southern Africa in the Cape Peninsula to Beira in Mocambique [440]. Female-biased sexual size dimorphism is the evolutionary trend [57].

Latitudinal and longitudinal species richness were tested for correlations with one another.

Materials and Methods

Latitude and longitude measurements for 40 species of southern African *Centrobolus* were obtained from published material. Species richness (per three degrees) was calculator using a Histogram plotter. A correlation between latitude with longitude and latitudinal species richness with longitudinal species richness was generated from the data given (Appendix 1-3).

Results

Latitude was correlated with longitude (Fig. 1: $r=0.73230860$, Z score=5.67940057, $n=40$, $p=0.00000001$).

Fig. 1. Longitude (x) and latitude (y) correlated across therange of *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

Latitude was correlated with species richness (Fig. 2: $r=-0.96813212$, Z score= -12.54035004 , $n=40$, $p=0$; Fig. 3)

Fig. 2. Latitude (x) and species richness (y) correlated across the range of *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

Fig. 3. Histogram showing species richness (y) across latitude in red millipedes.

Longitude was related to species richness (Fig. 4: $r=0.49062963$, Z score= 3.26576976 , $n=40$, $p=0.00054590$; Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Correlation between longitude (x) and species richness (y) across therange of *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

Fig. 5. Histogram showing species richness (y) across longitude in *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

Latitudinal species richness was related to longitudinal species richness in *Centrobolus* (Fig. 6: $r=0.3794$, $r^2=0.1439$, $n=40$, $p=0.01576$).

Fig. 6. Correlation between latitudinal species richness (x) and longitudinal species richness (y) across therange of *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

Discussion

There is a tie-in among species richness which is latitudinal and longitudinal in *Centrobolus*. This occurs because there are correlations between species richness and latitude and longitude.

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32.0377, -28.7830
 30.4550, -30.7414
 32.4167, -25.6000
 29.9947, -29.3561
 32.2833, -28.0333
 25.3961, -33.7674
 18.9833, -33.6333
 28.4319, -32.6292
 25.0630, -29.0460
 28.62377, -31.4648
 32.41667, -25.6000
 25.0630, -29.0460
 29.5448, -31.6229
 18.4212, -33.9212
 30.8667, -24.5833
 29.3235, -29.0755
 32.9876, -20.0092
 29.5448, -31.6229.

Appendix 1.

Longitude (degrees) and latitude (degrees) across the range of *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

30.7856, -26.1439
 26.5328, -33.3042
 30.6500, -30.4500
 20.0000, -34.0000
 31.0894, -28.6225
 24.6727, -28.4793
 31.4000, -27.8667
 18.3500, -34.0333
 19.3500, -34.5833
 24.6727, -28.4793
 32.0377, -28.7830
 33.1725, -18.9764
 32.3167, -28.3833
 31.0292, -29.8579
 30.3928, -29.61679
 25.8333, -33.8333
 35.3833, -23.8650
 25.61494, -33.9611
 23.8934, -34.0232
 20.0000, -34.0000
 18.34347, -34.0168
 28.4319, -32.6292

Appendix 2.

Latitudinal species richness in *Centrobolus* Cook, 1897.

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14	15
9	2
11	15
4	15
11	15
9	8
14	2
14	8
14	1
11	7
11	7
4	7
11	15
11	15
14	15
4	7
11	15
1	8
11.	7
Appendix 3.	7
Longitudinal species richness in <i>Centrobolus</i> Cook, 1897.	8
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15	8
7	7
15	7
8	15
15	7
7	15
7	7.
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